

Donor Behaviour of some Morpholine-*N*-thiohydrazones with some Bivalent Metal Ions

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In pursuance of our interest towards complexing behaviour of thiohydrazide and thiohydrazones^{1,2}, we report here the complexes of bivalent Cu, Co, Ni, Zn, Cd or Pd with benzaldehyde morpholine-*N*-thiohydrazone (BMTH), cinnamaldehyde morpholine-*N*-thiohydrazone (CINMTH) and cyclohexanone morpholine-*N*-thiohydrazone (CYMTH). These thiohydrazones (LH) have donor sites similar to the corresponding thiosemicarbazones (BH) but alkyl substitution on (-CS-NH₂) nitrogen contributes large electron density on sulphur atom and makes them better donor molecules for metal ions.

Results and Discussion

The colour, solubility in organic solvents, magnetic moment values and electronic spectra of [ML₂] (M = Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, LH = BMTH, CINMTH, CYMTH) complexes (Table 1) differ appreciably from each other depending on the nature of substituents on thiohydrazones. The Schiff base of cyclohexanone forms crystalline product with bright lustre. The ligand CYMTH forms neutral bis-chelate at higher pH while the others do so at lower pH. In neutral ethanolic medium, CYMTH gave [Cu(CYMTH)Cl₂] with copper(II) chloride whereas other ligands gave neutral bis-chelate [CuL₂] (LH = BMTH or CINMTH). The neutral bis-chelates of CYMTH were formed in basic medium. Cadmium(II) chloride formed [Cd(LH)Cl₂] (LH = BMTH, CINMTH or CYMTH) in neutral solution but in basic medium these changed to neutral bis-chelate CdL₂. [Co(CYMT)₂] is bright green crystalline product while [CoL₂] (LH = BMTH or CINMTH) are dark brown in colour.

[NiL₂] (LH = BMTH or CINMTH or CYMTH) and [CuL₂] (LH = BMTH or CINMTH) are brick-red while [Cu(CYMT)₂] is grey. The marked change in colour of the Co^{II} complex with BMTH and CINMTH can be attributed to hyperconjugation which is absent in CYMTH. In general, the complexes are insoluble in water but dissolve slightly in ethanol and methanol. The solubility of CYMTH complexes is higher in organic solvents than others. In DMF the electrical conductance values of the complexes are negligible, indicating their non-ionic character. The complexes of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pd^{II} are diamagnetic. The diamagnetism of the Pd^{II} complexes indicates their square-planar structure³. The room temperature magnetic moment values of the Co^{II} complexes (4.08–4.52 B.M.) and the Ni^{II} complexes (3.20–3.32 B.M.) occur in the range of tetrahedral geometry of complexes⁴. The Cu^{II} complexes display magnetic moment values 1.84–1.91 B.M., which suggests that they are magnetically dilute and probably possess a tetrahedral structure⁵.

Electronic absorption spectra of the ligands (Table 1) showed strong absorption bands at 200–330 nm due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The absorption bands of ligand are affected appreciably in position and intensity in their metal complexes. In solution the $d-d$ transitions expected for the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes [ML₂] were not observed in the visible region but [Co(CYMT)₂] showed a strong band at 630 nm assignable to $^4A_2 \rightarrow ^4T_1$ transition in tetrahedral field. The ligand field band of the BMTH and CINMTH complexes of Co^{II} could not be observed due to hyperconjugation in the ligand molecules.

The solid reflectance spectra of the Co^{II} , Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, however, display one broad band in the visible region (Table 1) attributed to $d-d$ transition in tetrahedral field⁶. From stoichiometry, magnetic susceptibility and spectral data, tetrahedral structure is suggested for the Co^{II} , Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes. From stoichiometry tetrahedral structure is also suggested for the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes which is the most favoured structure for elements with d^{10} electronic system⁷.

Table-1 (Contd)

$[\text{Zn}(\text{CYMT})_2]$	11 29	15 27	Dia	
(Cream white)	(11 97	15 39)		
$[\text{Cd}(\text{BMT})_2]$	17 29	13 54	Dia	235, 285, 348
(Cream white)	(18 46	13 80)		
$[\text{Cd}(\text{CINMT})_2]$	16 18	12 52	Dia	
(Cream white)	(17 00	12 71)		
$[\text{Cd}(\text{CYMT})_2]$	18 26	14 02	Dia	
(Cream white)	(18 95	14 17)		
$[\text{Cd}(\text{BMTH})\text{Cl}_2]$	25 24	9 60	Dia	
(Cream white)	(25 98	9 71)		
$[\text{Cd}(\text{CINMTH})\text{Cl}_2]$	23 89	9 09	Dia	
(Cream white)	(24 51	9 16)		
$[\text{Cd}(\text{CYMTH})\text{Cl}_2]$	25 60	9 66	Dia	
(Cream white)	(26 47	9 90)		

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd / Colour	Analysis %		μ_{eff} B M	λ_{max} (ϵ_{max}) nm
	Found/(Calcd)			
	Metal	N		
[BMTH]	—	16 77	Dia	225 (146 48),
(Cream white)	—	(16 85)		320 (22471)
[CINMTH]	—	15 19	Dia	235 (7127),
(Cream white)	—	(15 25)		330 (19438)
[CYMTH]	—	17 50	Dia	205 (7723), 275 (7165),
(Light orange)	—	(17 41)		328 (7014)
[Cu(BMT) ₂]	10 84	14 58	1 86	—
(Brick red)	(11 34	15 00)		
[Cu(CINMT) ₂]	10 21	13 26	1 91	200, 205, 220,
(Brick red)	(10 38	13 73)		340, 380
[Cu(CYMT) ₂]	11 65	15 40	1 88	203, 270, 870
(Grey)	(11 67	15 44)		
[Cu(CYMTH)Cl ₂]	16 98	10 90	1 84	750
(Dark brown)	(16 91	10 18)		
[Co(BMT) ₂]	10 57	15 08	3 98	660
(Dark brown)	(10 61	15 13)		
[Co(CINMT) ₂]	9 68	13 79	4 12	243, 295, 348,
(Dark brown)	(9 70	13 83)		383, 645
[Co(CYMT) ₂]	10 88	15 47	4 52	208, 270,
(Bright green)	(10 92	15 57)		630, 620
[Ni(BMT) ₂]	10 29	15 00	3 29	228, 270, 380,
(Brick red)	(10 57	15 13)		635, 715
[Ni(CINMT) ₂]	9 66	13 78	3 32	205, 260, 290, 330,
(Brick red)	(9 67	13 84)		390, 500, 680
[Ni(CYMT) ₂]	10 83	15 46	3 20	20 5, 272
(Brick red)	(10 88	15 52)		
[Pd(BMT) ₂]	17 96	14 13	Dia	
(Cream yellow)	(17 64	13 94)		
[Pd(CINMT) ₂]	15 89	13 01	Dia	
(Yellow)	(16 19	12 79)		
[Pd(CYMT) ₂]	17 82	14 14	Dia	
(Orange yellow)	(18 12	14 31)		
[Zn(BMT) ₂]	12 24	14 68	Dia	
(Cream white)	(11 63	14 95)		
[Zn(CINMT) ₂]	10 18	13 47	Dia	240, 290,
(Cream white)	(10 65	13 69)		380, 400

In the ir spectra, the solid ligands do not display S-H vibrations indicating the absence of thiol tautomer in solid state⁸. The ν_{NH} band of the ligands (3 130–3 180 cm^{-1}) disappeared in neutral bis-chelates while it was not affected appreciably in dichloro complexes $[\text{MLCl}_2]$. The azomethine (C=N) stretch of ligands observed at 1 570–1 590 cm^{-1} was raised to higher frequency in complexes by 10–15 cm^{-1} , indicating the coordination of C=N nitrogen with metal atom^{8,9}. The thioamide bands I (1 525–1 570), II (1 405–1 415) and III (1 065–1 110 cm^{-1}) of the complexes were raised to higher frequencies (1 545–1 595, 1 420–1 445, 1 090–1 305 cm^{-1} respectively) while thioamide band IV (870–925 cm^{-1}) shifted to lower frequency⁸ by 120–150 cm^{-1} in inner bis-chelates but it shifted by 30–40 cm^{-1} only in dichloro complexes. A large shift of thioamide band IV in neutral bis-chelates suggests the bonding of the ligand by deprotonated thiol sulphur while a small shift of thioamide band IV in dichloro complexes suggests the bonding through thione sulphur⁹. In far-infrared region, the ligands displayed a number of bands and therefore, no definite band positions for $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$, $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$ could be assigned¹⁰.

Experimental

Ligands BMTH, CINMTH and CYMTH were prepared by condensing aqueous methanolic solution of morpholine-*N*-thiohydrazone¹² with appropriate aldehyde or ketone in molar proportion in presence of a little acetic acid. The products were crystallised from methanol.

NOTE

[ML_2] ($M(II) = Cu, Co, Ni, Zn, Cd, Pd$; $LH = BMTH, CINMTH, CYMTH$) : The metal acetate or chloride (0.005 mol) dissolved in aqueous methanol (50%; 50 ml) was treated with hot methanolic solution of the ligand (0.01 mol in 30 ml). The pH of the resulting solution was adjusted to 7–8 by adding dilute ammonia and warmed on a steam-bath. The resulting solid was washed with methanol and dried over $CaCl_2$ and in an air-oven at 60–70°, (~98%).

[$Cu(CYMTH)Cl_2$] and [$Cd(LH)Cl_2$] ($LH = BMTH, CINMTH$ or $CYMTH$) : The metal chloride (0.005 mol) dissolved in hot methanol (30 ml) was treated with hot methanolic solution of the ligand with stirring. The solution was cooled in ice-cold water and the resulting solid was washed with cold methanol and dried over $CaCl_2$.

Magnetic susceptibility, conductance and spectral measurements were performed as reported earlier².

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References

1. B. N. KESHARI and L. K. MISHRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect.*

- A, 1981, **18**, 878; L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 1198.
2. R. N. PATHAK and L. K. MISHRA *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 119; K. DAS, U. S. PRASAD, A. K. DUBEY, B. N. KESHARI and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 497.
3. W. ROYMASON and H. B. GRAY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 5521.
4. R. S. NYHOLM and B. N. FIGGIS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 41.
5. E. FOSTAR and D. M. L. GOODGAME, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 823.
6. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1965.
7. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "An Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1966, p. 621.
8. I. SUZUKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1962, **35**, 1286, 1456.
9. D. VENKAPPYIA and D. H. BROWN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 1023.
10. R. D. BERFMAN, D. M. BAIRD, J. BORDNER and J. DOREMAN, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 25; M. K. DAS, M. NATH and J. J. ZUCKERMAN, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, **21**, 49.
11. D. M. ADAMS and J. B. CORNELL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 1299; M. GOLDSTFIN and W. D. UNSWORTH, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1970, **4**, 343.
12. V. YA. KASAKOVA and I. YA. POSTOVSKII, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk. SSR*, 1960, **134**, 824.

